

A STUDY OF LIFE SKILLS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN NAINITAL DISTRICT (UTTARAKHAND)

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Abstract

Life skills are the skills and abilities that allow people to deal with the challenges, difficulties, and circumstances of everyday existence. They assist a person in making informed decisions, solving problems, communicating effectively, managing emotions, developing healthy relationships, and dealing with stress in a constructive and responsible manner. Life skills are essential for adolescents to adequately cope with the demands and difficulties of everyday existence. Secondary education is a vital phase for the development of essential talents such as making decisions, problem-solving, interpersonal skills, and emotional regulation. Life skills give students the ability to integrate knowledge and beliefs in real-world situations, encouraging holistic development, self-reliance, and responsible engagement. The aim of this research is to assess the level of life skills among students in secondary schools in the Nainital District. The sample of this study was selected randomly 80 students studying in government and private schools in Nainital district. Life Skills Assessment Scale by Dr. Chandra Kumari and Ms. Ayushi Tripathi (2009) was used for the collection of data in the present study. The findings show that gender significantly influences life skills among the students; whereas the type of institution does not have a significant effect on their life skills thus the individuals show a reasonably good level of life skills with moderate individual variances. The study emphasizes the importance of systematically integrating life skills education into the school curriculum to support students' overall growth and well-being and gives suggestions for Schools and Administrators, Parents and Policymakers.

Keywords: Life Skills, Secondary School Students, Adolescents, Nainital District

1.0 Introduction:

In the rapidly evolving globe of the twenty-first century, education is expected to go beyond scholastic knowledge and nurture important life skills that will help students deal with real-life issues. Life skills are psychosocial abilities that allow people to make informed decisions, solve problems successfully, control their emotions, and develop positive relationships (World Health Organization [WHO], 1999). These skills are essential for personal and social growth, as they contribute to general well-being and success in professional, educational, and social contexts. Adolescence is a vital developmental stage marked by rapid physical growth, emotional changes, creation of identities, and increased social engagement. Adolescence, particularly secondary school, is a critical phase for learning life skills because of the major physical, emotional, and social changes adolescents encounter (Narayan, 2005). During this stage, adolescents confront academic pressure, peer influence, job uncertainty, and emotional stress, emphasizing the importance of teaching them critical thinking, communication, decision-making, and stress management skills (UNICEF, 2012).

Life skills education is becoming increasingly important in Indian education as part of a holistic development approach. The National Curriculum Framework (NCF, 2005) emphasizes the value of developing life skills in order to equip students for meaningful and responsible involvement in society. Furthermore, researchers contend that structured life skills education boosts students' self-

awareness, resilience, and problem-solving ability (Aggarwal, 2015; Sharma & Sharma, 2018). Several researchers have found a substantial link between life skills and children's academic achievement, mental health, and social interaction. According to Goleman (1995), emotional abilities such as self-awareness, empathy, and emotional control are often more important in determining life success than cognitive intelligence. Aggarwal (2015) claims that life skills education promotes holistic development by encouraging critical thinking, problem-solving ability, interpersonal skills, and ethical beliefs among students. These qualities help students utilize classroom learning in real-world circumstances and make responsible decisions. Life skills education is gaining more attention in the Indian educational system, especially with the focus on learner-centered and holistic approaches. In order to prepare students for lifelong learning, social peace, and democratic engagement, the National Curriculum Framework (NCF, 2005) emphasizes the importance of incorporating life skills into the curriculum. Additionally, UNICEF (2012) emphasizes that life skills education helps teenagers develop resilience, self-worth, and social responsibility, which lowers risk behaviors and fosters healthy youth development.

Districts like Nainital in Uttarakhand provide special educational opportunities and difficulties because they span a variety of socioeconomic backgrounds and geographical terrains. Different amounts of exposure, support networks, and educational resources may be available to students in these areas. In order to identify strengths, gaps, and areas that need assistance, it is crucial to comprehend the level of life skills among secondary school students in Nainital District. The current study aims to analyze the life skills of secondary school students in Nainital District in order to contribute to inform educational planning and effective secondary life skills education implementation.

2.0 Significance of the study:

Education plays an important role for human development. School education influences a child's personality. Adolescents face uncertain prospects due to societal pressures, environmental changes, and lack of resources. The 21st century brings enormous global transitions and changes. Adolescents are particularly impacted. Adolescents, the future of our country, require strong life skills. The research on life skills among secondary school students in the Nainital District is significant because it emphasizes the significance of critical life skills like communication, problem-solving, decision-making, and stress management during adolescence. The study gives educators, administrators, and policymaker's significant data to improve life skills education in the educational system by evaluating secondary school students' life skills. The results can help create learner-centered, holistic, and competency-based teaching strategies that improve the performance of learners in school, their mental wellness, and social adjustment. Furthermore, by providing context-specific findings from the Nainital district, the study closes a regional research gap and provides a valuable resource for future research and educational planning.

3.0 Review of Literature: Beni, Iuliano, and Visek (2021)

provide an overview of the SCORES Project, which investigates the implementation of life skill development through youth sports in several nations. The study underlines that sports are an effective non-formal setting for developing psychosocial skills such as teamwork, communication, emotional control, and conflict resolution. It emphasizes the importance of focused instruction and organized reflection by coaches, rather than incidental learning, in transferring these abilities to academic and family settings, as well as the necessity for standardized coach training to assure effective and consistent life skills education.

Arora and Singh (2020) studied 350 CBSE students from North India to investigate the influence of emotional intelligence and life skills on academic stress. Using standardized scales, the study discovered that both characteristics significantly predicted stress levels, implying that students with better emotional regulation and coping skills had lower academic stress. The findings emphasize the complimentary significance of emotional intelligence and life skills in handling academic challenges and advocate for the incorporation of these competences into school curricula to lessen students' susceptibility to stress.

Rani Sonu and Neeraj (2020) in their research "A study on life skill of senior secondary students" compared the life skills of senior secondary students on the basis of gender by using random sampling and Life Skill Scale developed by M.N. Vranda (2009). The main conclusions of the study show that while communication abilities are equivalent for both genders, female students outperform their male counterparts in decision-making, problem-solving, empathy, interpersonal relationships, and emotional management.

Nasheeda, Abdullah, Krauss, and Ahmed (2019) carried out an organized review of 25 empirical studies to assess the efficacy of life skills programs for adolescents. The review discovered consistent favorable results in managing stress, academic motivation, and emotional regulation, indicating that life skills education consistently improves student well-being. The findings confirm that such treatments are beneficial in a variety of cultural contexts, emphasizing the importance of incorporating psychosocial skills into school curricula to increase student involvement and coping capacity.

Smitha and Thomas (2018) used a self-constructed questionnaire to assess life skills awareness among postgraduate students. The findings imply that including life skills such as problem solving, decision-making, empathy, communication, and stress management into education improves learning quality. Life skill practices and social activities promote excellent educator-student interactions.

4.0. Objectives of the Study:

1. To study the status of life skills among secondary school students in Nainital district.
2. To compare the life skills of secondary school students of Nainital district based on gender.
3. To compare the life skills of secondary school students of Nainital district based on the type of school.

5.0. Hypothesis of the Study:

1. There is no significant difference between the life skills of secondary school students of Nainital district based on gender
2. There is no significant difference between the life skills of secondary school students of Nainital district based on the type of school

6.0. Limitations of the Study:

- The study was delimited to Nainital district only.
- The study was delimited to secondary school students only.
- The study was delimited to 80 students for secondary level only.

7.0. Research Method:

In the current study, the researcher uses the Survey method. The study is conducted on a sample of 80 students from 4 educational institutions (2 government and 2 private). In our study, the

population consists of all students in secondary school (grades through 12) in Nainital district of Uttarakhand . The Uttarakhand government’s RTE portal shows that there are 3910 registered schools in the state. Nainital district has eight blocks: Betalghat, Kotabagh, Haldwani, Bhimtal, Dhari, Ramnagar, Ramgarh, and Okhalkanda. The population includes both male and female students. The four schools are GGIC Haldwani, Shishu Bharti Vidya Mandir, Cynthia Sr. Sec. School, Woodland’s Global School. Random sampling is used to collect data from these schools.

7.1. Tool of data collection: The data is collected using Life Skills Assessment Scale developed by Dr. Chandra Kumari and Ms. Ayushi Tripathi. This scale is based on the World Health Organization's core framework, which includes essential domains such as decision-making, problem solving, interpersonal relationships, effective communication, stress and emotion management, self-awareness, creative thinking, and critical thinking. It comprises of 52 items designed to assess how well an individual possesses and applies these fundamental abilities in daily life. The assessment employs a Likert-type response structure, allowing for quantitative evaluation of life skill skills. It is especially beneficial in educational and psychological settings to evaluate the effectiveness of life skills training programs and identify areas that require additional growth or intervention.

7.2. Statistics used: Mean, Standard Deviation,t-test are the statistics used in this research.

8.0. Analysis and Findings:

Table 8.1 Status of Life Skills among secondary school students in Nainital district

Group	N	Mean (x̄)	SD (s)	t-value	df	p-value	Conclusion (α=0.05)
Male	40	175.75	30.15	2.01	78	0.048	Reject H ₀
Female	40	160.33	29.50				

The mean score of Life Skills is 168.04, indicating that, on average, the participants possess a moderately high level of life skills. This mean value suggests that the overall life skills of the sample are above the average level and reflect a generally satisfactory development of life skills among the participants. The standard deviation is 30.55, which signifies a moderate level of variability in the scores. This implies that while many participants scored close to the mean, there are also participants whose life skills are either significantly higher or lower than the average. Overall, the descriptive analysis reveals that the participants demonstrate a fairly good level of life skills with moderate individual differences

Table 8.2 H01- Life Skills of secondary school students of Nainital district based on gender

Group	N	Mean (x̄)	SD (s)	t-value	df	p-value	Conclusion (α=0.05)
Male	40	175.75	30.15	2.01	78	0.048	Reject H ₀
Female	40	160.33	29.50				

The calculated t -value is 2.01 with 78 degrees of freedom, and the corresponding p -value is 0.048. Since the p -value is less than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. This indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in Life Skills between male and female participants. The results further reveal that male participants scored significantly higher on Life Skills than female participants. Therefore, it can be concluded that gender has a significant effect on Life Skills among the participants included in the study.

Table 7.3 H02- Life Skills of secondary school students of Nainital district based on the type of School.

Group	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD (s)	t-value	df	p-value	Conclusion ($\alpha=0.05$)
Private	40	170.80	25.12	0.70	78	0.485	Fail to Reject H_0
Government	40	165.28	35.15				

The mean Life Skills score of students from private institutions was 170.80 with a standard deviation of 25.12, while students from government institutions obtained a mean score of 165.28 with a standard deviation of 35.15. Although the mean score of private institution students appears slightly higher than that of government institution students, the difference is relatively small. The calculated t -value is 0.70 with 78 degrees of freedom, and the corresponding p -value is 0.485. Since the p -value is greater than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is not rejected. This result indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in Life Skills between students of private and government institutions. Therefore, it can be concluded that the type of institution does not have a significant influence on the Life Skills of the students included in the study.

9.0. Conclusions and Suggestions:

The main aim of the research is to study the Life Skills among Secondary School Students in Nainital District. The following suggestions are given for the improvement:

Suggestions for Educational Institutions (Schools and Administrators)

- **Mandatory, Structured Life Skills Curriculum:** Schools must move beyond informal instruction and incorporate a formal, planned Life Skills Education (LSE) program into their main curriculum. This should cover the WHO-defined categories of stress management, emotional control, critical thinking, and effective communication. According to the gender gap findings, these programs should contain courses that expressly address the unique stressors that female students face, such as handling social pressures, balancing expectations, and building assertiveness.
- **Trained Faculty:** Faculty members must undergo required professional development in stress diagnosis and management strategies, especially those who teach secondary grades. In order to model critical thinking and healthy coping mechanisms during difficult academic work, teachers should be trained to identify the early signs of burnout and anxiety, particularly in female students, and to incorporate LSE ideas into academic courses (infusion approach).

- **Promoting a Multi-Functional Assessment Culture:** Administrators should push for and implement a system that prioritizes several assessments rather than just high-stakes exams. Implementing project-based learning, portfolios, and ongoing formative assessment can help reduce performance anxiety and shift the emphasis away from rote learning and toward competency and skill development.

Suggestions for Parents and Family

- **Awareness Campaigns on Pressure:** According to Deb, Strodl, and Sun (2015b), parents must get clear education about the detrimental effects of high and unyielding academic demands on their children's mental health. To assist parents in distinguishing between support and excessive pressure, workshops ought to be arranged.
- **Promoting Autonomy:** Parents need to be urged to help their children develop their capacity for self-control and judgment. The study's emphasis on life skills suggests that children develop the resilience required to meet academic demands when they are given the freedom to control their schedule and deal with small setbacks. The development of self-sufficient coping strategies is particularly important for female students.
- **Encouraging a Positive Home Environment:** The home should be a haven from the pressures of school. A favorable, low-stress environment is a significant non-cognitive predictor of performance and well-being, as demonstrated by Sharma & Chouhan (2008).

Suggestions for Policymakers and Curriculum Developers

- **Gender-Specific Policy Directives:** State-level education policies need to issue directives requiring LSE programs that take into account the known gender disparities in stress management and coping mechanisms. Areas with weaker psychological resources, such as Nainital, should be given priority when allocating resources.
- **Validation of Life Skills:** Curriculum committees require to create consistent, trustworthy measures for evaluating life skills (beyond the research phase) and acknowledge them as fundamental learning objectives, on line with academic grades. This acknowledgment would encourage schools to invest time and resources in LSE.
- **Mental Health Support Infrastructure:** Policies must encourage the development of specialized, professional counseling services within secondary schools, guaranteeing the availability of qualified psychologists who can offer focused intervention for students experiencing academic pressure, given the moderate to high stress levels.

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